

Gandhi's Antipathy with Swarajists During Freedom Struggle

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The old-style Congress, a federation of provincial grandees, was being destroyed by Gandhi's consolidation of the powers of the All-India Congress executive and his intrusions into provincial politics.¹³⁸ His new appeals had won him the support of the social groups which previously had no share in nationalist politics. The dynamics underlying the emergence of these were unclear but there were significant Indian social change in the second decade of the twentieth century. Gandhi drew his most solid support from areas which formerly had played no major part in the nationalist movement, and, in the old nationalist regions, from social groups which had formerly no voice in nationalist policy. The elite were uncomfortable with the new language and symbolism of mass politics which Gandhi had introduced to Indian nationalism. The elite resisted Gandhi's ambition to use the extended powers of a reconstructed Congress to achieve his vision.

Direct Conflict between Pro Changers and No Changers

C.R. Das and Motilal Nehru and all other leaders who had been sentenced in December 1921 for refusing to honour the Prince of Wales were released from Jail in the year 1922. They saw before them the plight of the Congress which they had themselves built up so laboriously by the sacrifice of all that they valued in life.¹ The origin of the Swarajists, however, really dates back to the times of the infamous Chauri-Chaura outrage in February 1922.² After Gandhi's imprisonment, Chitta Ranjan broached to his fellow-prisoners the idea of Congressmen going into the councils and Shyam Sunder Chakravarti who was also there in the Alipore Jail, entered into a very bitter controversy with him over this matter.³ The release of the leaders gave rise to a bigger controversy over the issue of council entry and for eight months preceding September, 1923, when the Swaraj Party obtained recognition from the Congress, an internecine quarrel with the Congress continued to this. This prolonged discussion brought the ideological differences between Motilal Nehru and C.R. Das, on the one hand, and Mahatma Gandhi and 'no-changers' on the other, to the forefront of public imagination. Motilal Nehru, C.R. Das, Hakim Ajmal Khan and Vitthalbhai J. Patel were definitely in favour of the policy of entering councils and wrecking the constitution and they were designated as 'pro-changers'. M.A. Ansari, K.R. Iyengar and C. Rajagopalachari of the no-changers, however attached dyarchy, C.R. Das regarded it as an attempt of the British Parliament to force a foreign system upon the Indian people. He, therefore, wished that councils should either be mended or ended. "Hitherto" said he, "we have been boycotting the Councils from outside...It should be the duty of the Congress to boycott the councils more

effectively from within. Reformed Councils are really a mask which the Bureaucracy has put on.⁴ The Congress boycott of the councils in 1920, argued C.R. Das, had done much; their prestige was diminished and the country knew that the people who adorned these chambers were not their true representatives. But, in spite of it all, the councils were still there. Such steps, should, therefore, be taken that they might not be there to impede the progress of Swaraj. The boycott of foreign goods could hardly be effective without taking such steps as there might be no foreign goods in the Indian markets.⁵

The Swarajists did not agree to the idea that the very entry into the Councils was inconsistent with the idea of non-cooperation. Supposing the Congress had sanctioned an armed insurrection, it could not be argued that entry into the fort of the bureaucracy was inconsistent with the principles of fighting, for "advancing army does not cooperate with the enemy when it marches into the enemy's territory."⁶ The entire fallacy in the argument of inconsistency was based on the assumption that entry into the Councils automatically implied cooperation. C.R. Das regarded entry into the councils to co-operate with the Government as altogether different from entry into the councils to non-cooperate.

The 'pro-changers' also refuted the contention that entering councils with the object of emasculating them offended against morality, it was unfair or dishonest as well. The very manner of entering them with the object of ending them absolved the followers of the council-entry from all guilt of dishonesty. C.R. Das, "I admit if we had proposed to enter the councils stealthily, with the avowed object of cooperation, but keeping within on hearts the desire to break the councils, such a course would undoubtedly have been dishonest...If we play now, we play with all our cards on the table."⁷ It's immortality on the ground that it involved an idea of destruction was untenable, for the principle of obstruction countenanced destruction as well as construction. "As a matter of fact," said Das, "Circumstances as we are with the Bureaucracy all round us, it is impossible to create without destroying, nor must, it be forgotten that if we break, it only that we may build."⁸ Nor was the programme of Council-entry, in any way, antagonistic to spiritual considerations. The basis of spirituality for Indians must be the attainment of Swaraj. C.R.'s confirmed view was that no activity in isolation could bring Swaraj and it was the totality of our national activity in the way of creation and in the way of destruction, that would do it.⁹ He regarded the councils as instruments for the propagation of British tyranny and he warned his countrymen against the policy of allowing the Reformed councils to work their wicked will.¹⁰

The Swarajists, however, were not merely for destructive work. Both C.R.Das and

Motilal believed that constructive work was essential for the uplift of the country and they openly declared their faith in it. But they did not believe that it alone would bring Swaraj within a reasonable time.¹¹ Motilal Nehru made it clear that it would always be his party's endeavour to help Gandhi in his constructive work. But he also plainly asserted that the Swarajists were not prepared to give up their rights and allow a small majority to change the Congress constitution and its free will to crush a large minority.¹² The Chairman, Reception Committee Gaya Session of the Indian National Congress held in 1923, emphasised that the programme of non-cooperation itself had two aspects – positive or constructive or negative or destructive. "But", said he, "if we focus our energies only on destructive or negative aspect; we shall not be able to visualise the real, which is the constructive aspect of the movement and can never hope to reach our goal."¹³ In spite of such an attitude of the Swarajists towards constructive programme of Gandhi, the Chairman, however, lamented that some gentlemen who were opposed to council entry, had taken to vilify leaders and workers who held different views on this question.¹⁴

Five Intensified in 1923

The 'no-changers' really had no soft corner for the Swarajists' programme and they were diametrically opposed to their views. They believed that the scheme of non-cooperation would be disturbed altogether in the event of permitting entry into the councils.¹⁵ Even Gandhi was no exception. He declared, "After having discussed with Swarajist friends the vexed question of entry into the legislative Assembly and councils by Congressmen, I am sorry to have to say that I have not been able to see eye to eye with the Swarajist position."¹⁶ He said,, "I assure the public that there has been no lack of willingness of effect on my part to accept the Swarajist position. My task would be much simpler if I could identify myself with it. It can be no pleasure to me to oppose even in thought the most valued and respected leaders, some of whom have made great sacrifices in the cause of the country."¹⁷ There is an honest and fundamental difference, I retain the opinion that council entry is inconsistent with non-cooperation as I conceive it. Nor is this difference more a matter of interpretation of the word non cooperation but relates to the essential mental attitude resulting in difference treatment of vital problems. It is with reference to such mental attitude that the success or the failure of the triple boycott is to be judged and not merely by reversing to the actual results attained.¹⁸ It is from that point of view that I say that to be out of legislative bodies is for more advantages to the country than to be in them.¹⁹ I have, however, failed to contains my Swarajist friends. But I recognize that so long as they think otherwise, their place is

undoubtedly in the councils. It is the best for us all'.²⁰ He further added, It was hardly to be expected that the Swarajists could be convinced by the arguments that I advanced in the course of conversations. They are many of them, amongst the ablest, most experienced and honest patriots. They have not entered the legislative bodies without full deliberations and they must not be expected to retire from the position until experience has convinced them of the futility of their method.²¹

Gandhi wanted the no changers to remain true to their faith by prosecuting the constructive programme with undivided energy and concentration and justify their opposition to council entry only by showing the results of their application to the constructive work.²² He was positively dissatisfied with the attitude of disregard that the Swarjists had towards Khaddar. It disturbed him to find that several of them had said a final good-bye to Khaddar and that the material of which their dress was made was foreign. He was convinced beyond doubt that his constructive programme alone could bring Swaraj to India and that the councils could only give condiments but no bread.²³ Towards the realization of the goal of Swaraj, the policy of council entry would yield no substantial results²⁴ and he, therefore, did not agree to it.²⁵ Non-cooperation was the creed of his life. "It is", said he, "not merely a policy with me, it is an article of faith".²⁶ He added, "This Salyagraha did not fail me in South Africa, Kheda or Champaran and in a host of other cases I could mention."²⁷ The implication was quite natural that it would also not fail in the case of India. A tried path, he believed was better than a plunge into the dark. Emasculating the councils was, to Gandhi, a far cry and was full of contingencies.

Next to Gandhi, C. Rajagopalachari could easily occupy the first place among the 'no-changes' in point of Vigorous opposition to the 'pro-changers'. He was a staunch non-cooperator and he believed that the boycott of the councils in 1920 has destroyed the moral strength of the institutions through which Government sought to consolidate its power and carry its irresponsible rule.²⁸ He was, therefore, eager that India withheld participation in the elections of the year 1923 as well. He said, "Treat the councils with indifference and that is the most effective manner in which this nation when once it has resolved upon boycotting the councils can boycott them."²⁹ M.A. Ansari wished the people to further the cause of non-cooperation for it was full of the possibilities of success. Only by creating an atmosphere of real boycott of the councils could the country be prepared for the next step of civil Disobedience Movement.³⁰

The 'no-changers' were not prepared to believe that boycott from within was boycott

at all. They identified boycott of councils with complete withdrawal from them and C.R. Das's argument that to be effective the range of boycott should be extended to emasculating them from within had no appeal to them. Even Muhammad Ali preferred to hold strong views on the subject of the triple boycott of councils, law courts and schools and colleges and did not abstain himself from giving expression to them in strong language in the course of discussion. He said, "I hold the same view today and would gladly give expression to them again in equally strong language, if I could be convinced that it was necessary in the best interest of the Congress and the country."³¹ To him the Swaraj Party was the embodiment of the depression experienced by all India when Gandhi, after having brought the country to the very door of Swaraj, suddenly declared that it was unwise to force that door by resorting to mass civil disobedience.³²

The sponsors of the Swaraj Party, Motilal Nehru and C.R. Das. had enough justification to try a new method of facing the Government. The circumstances of the sudden withdrawal of the non-cooperation movement and the 'no-changers' reliance on mere constructive programme stood in need of being supplemented by something vigorous to capture the public imagination. The creed of non-violent non-cooperation had become an irrefutable gospel with them but it brought about a sense of repulsion in others. C.R. Das only represented the feelings of the opposite group in the Congress when he said, "Non-cooperation do not touch a bit of it lest the sacred thing may wither."³³ C.R. Das remarked, "What do I care about the Congress when the fate of my country is threatened?.... I want 'Swaraj', I want liberty I have left my practice, I have left every business save the business of Swaraj".³⁴

Gandhi as a Congress President of Belgaun Congress

When Gandhi was released from jail in February, 1924, all eyes turned to him for leadership and for the establishment of real unity in and outside the Congress.³⁵ He spent some time in Juhu and his talks with Moti Lal Nehru and Das went on for some time, raising hopes of fresh agreement.³⁶ Gandhi was left unconvinced of the Swarajists' position.

He went to attend the Ahmedabad meeting of the All India Congress Committee in June, 1924, with full determination to conquer the Swarajists, but he left in tears 'defeated and humbled.'³⁷ After his defeat, he, however, backed that up with all his strength and ultimately made them the accredited agents of the Congress to deal with the Government.³⁸ By November, 1924 Gandhi had reconciled himself with the Swarajists so much that he was

able to say, "I thank God that he gave me strength to surrender to the Swarajists all that it was possible for me to surrender much more than I or my friends expected. I must acknowledge my indebtedness to the Swarjists for their accommodation".³⁹ He realized that the 'no-changers' were intensely dissatisfied with the agreement entered into with the Swarajist,⁴⁰ but he was fully alive to their truly pathetic position.¹⁸³ The perplexing of 'no-changers' continued unabated. They felt that Mahatma had probably given up even life-long principles for patchwork.⁴¹

At the Belgaum Congress in December, 1924 (Where Gandhi presided), the way was, therefore, prepared for the achievement of a signal success in remaining mistrial in suspicion and antagonism. He openly said that he had concluded a pact with the Swarajists and, in doing so, he had not committed any mistake.⁴² The agreement incorporated the suspension of the programme of non-cooperation except in so far as it related to the refusal to use or wear cloth made out of India and the substitution of the spinning franchise for the money franchise,⁴³ which laid down that different kinds of Congress work might be done by different sections within the organisation. Gandhi said, "If I was not to divide the Congress on the issue of its status, I was bound to agree to its conditions."⁴⁴ Nilkantan Namboodiripad had made it plain "In spite of all my personal opinion against council-entry, I do not want the country to be divided. I am really grieved to see the conflict within our ranks."⁴⁵ It was in this frame of mental attitude that Belgaum finally settled all disputes between the two conflicting groups in the Congress. Thus was born the Swaraj Party through the vigorous efforts of Moti Lal Nehru and C.R. Das. It kept the British government paralyzed for some time and maintained the spirit of resistance alive in the country. Its task was by no means easy as it had to fight almost simultaneously on both fronts-inside the Congress against 'no-changers' and outside it against the British Government.

Gandhi's Antipathy with Marathi Leadership

Between 1919 and 1937, politicians utilized social and economic developments to form a new Congress in the Marathi region. Gandhi himself inaugurated this venture by persuading some urban leaders to join in a nation-wide Satyagraha in 1919 against the Rowlatt Act, a measure giving the Government of India arbitrary powers to deal with sedition.⁴⁶ This call evoked a little response from the Tilakites, who were unwilling to allow Gandhi to weaken their influence or threaten their style of politics, but it did win the support

of men on the periphery of political life. Gandhi moved to undermine the Tilakites' hold on politics in the Marathi region. He won his first victory when, in response to his call to politicians and voters to boycott the elections to the reformed legislature in December, most Tilakites withdraw from the contest.⁴⁷ They did so because politicians in other parts of India had withdrawn, and because it was possible that voters would snub them if they defied Gandhi.⁴⁸

The annual session of the Congress marked a further stage in the establishment of Gandhi's influence over the Congress in the Marathi region.⁴⁹ Moonje and Kharparde were confident that the delegates from Bombay, Bengal and Punjab would join them in opposing non-cooperation, but at the last minute Gandhi secured the support of many of these politicians. These alliances, the large numbers already committed to Gandhi, and the emotional atmosphere reduced Moonje and other opponents of non-cooperation to impotence.⁵⁰ As a result, the All India Congress Committee and the delegates at the open session voted overwhelmingly to support non-cooperation and the new Congress constitution devised by Gandhi, and in doing so committed Marathi Congressmen to a style of politics which most of them abhorred.

In the socially-competitive Marathi region, social and economic developments fostered the growth of rival political organizations, among them the new Congress. Of these, the Congress became the leading organization by 1937, eclipsing the Tilakites by coining support among the middle and working classes in the towns, and among landowners, peasants and labourers in the countryside. Despite this the Tilakites were able to reorganize their forces after 1925, while groups of non-Brahmins, Harijans and Muslims formed political organizations to further their sectional interests in co-operation with the government. Though these bodies did not defeat the Congress, they did deprive it of the support of important sections of society, and so weakened its overall position in provincial politics.

Tambe's acceptance of the Home membership in 1925 marked a turning point in the fortunes of the Tilakites in the Marathi Region. Until then they had shared membership of the Congress with the Gandhians, though relations between the two were marked by increasing friction. The Tilakites had faced additional opposition from non-Brahman politicians who sought to undermine the dominant position enjoyed by Brahmins, and from

Harijans who demanded that Hindus accord them social recognition and greater economic opportunities. Moreover, the Tilakites believed that the Muslims, who were playing an increasing part in politics, posed a threat to the Hindu community. Unable to counter the activities of these groups through the Congress, Moonje and the Tilakites followed Tambe's lead by striking out on an independent course, creating bodies to advance the interests of Hindus and Harijans alike and weld them into a single political and social force. Like Tambe, they sought to achieve these goals through responsive co-operation with the government.⁵¹

To launch these ventures into the Nagpur division, Moonje utilized men drawn from various castes and sections of society. His closest associates were Maharashtrian Brahmin professional men, who were able to exploit the appeal of Tilak and their own connections with caste, class, professions and land to develop support among the urban middle-classes and landowners whose interests they represented. Moonje also secured the support of several old landed and banking families⁵² who were concerned about countering the populist tendencies in the Congress and the growing cleavages in Marathi society. Besides these, he attracted to his political circle influential non-Brahmins and⁵³ Mahar leaders, aiming thereby to harness the support of their followers for his new initiative.

On this diversified, social base, Moonje and the Tilakites built their political organizations. Central to these was the Responsive Party formed in 1926, to contest elections to the Provincial legislature against the Congress on the question of accepting office in the government. At these elections the responsive Party, as it was also known, heavily defeated the Congress, and at Moonje's instance, entered into a coalition with the Independent Congress Party, and with Harijans, Independents and non-Brahmins in order to form a ministry.⁵⁴ This coalition was known as the Nationalist Party, a term which the Tilakites in Berar continued to use of themselves after the coalition was dissolved in 1928. In 1934, Tilakites in the region also formed the Democratic Swarajya Party to contest elections in the Central legislative Assembly in that year.

As for the non-Brahmins, Moonje gave leading non-Brahman politicians positions of responsibility in Responsive organizations and allowed them to articulate the views of the non-Brahmin community. He also secured the support the Bhonsle royal family for his political ventures, besides anointing the influential chitnavis family with the Nationalist coalition and other activities outside the legislature. In this way, he hoped to obviate the development of sectional politics and channellise non-Brahmin energies into the Responsive

cause. Moonje also attracted Mahar organizations to his political movement through his association with G.A. Gavi,⁵⁵ a leading Mahar from Amravati. A journalist, Gavai was nominated by the government to the legislative in 1920, and in 1926 became leader of the Marathi branch of the All India Depressed classes Association, a body which aimed to advance the social and economic well being of Harijans. Moonje and his associates besides endeavored to attract groups within the working classes in Nagpur into these political organizations. Prominent among these groups were the Koshti weavers and the Mahar and other mill workers, with whom Gandhians also sought to form connections. To establish contact with these groups, Moonje utilized the services of G.A. Ogala, editor of the Maharashtra, Dr. L.V. Pranjpe, a forceful orator, and the wealthy pleader, G.V. Deshmukh. In the early days of trade union movement in Nagpur these politicians frequently addressed workers' meetings and sought to form trade unions amenable to Responsive influence, securing representation on the trade union Congress established in 1928.⁵⁶

Although the orthodox Congress had come to dominate Marathi politics by 1937, there were also other important organizations in the region's political life. These bodies opposed the Congress and participated in the British political arenas, and in doing so, deprived the Congress of support from important sections of society and also weakened its influence in the province. As a result, the Marathi Congress lost ground to the Hindi Congress which developed after 1919 as the only effective party in its region, and which despite the presence of factions was well placed to dominate a government formed after the Assembly elections in 1937.

The historical impact of Gandhian ideology and the evolution of Indian politics was of monumental significance. The experimental conception of truth, combining the absolute moral legitimacy of Satyagraha with the tactical considerations of ahimsa made the Gandhian ideology into a powerful instrument in the historical task of constructing the new India state.⁵⁷ While it was the Gandhian intervention in the elite nationalist politics in India, which established for the first time, that an authentic national movement could only be built upon the organized support of the whole of the peasantry.

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